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Abstract: The article examines the criteria for assessing the level of assimilation of educational materials by students based on the international assessment program “Programme for International Student Assessment” (PISA).

Keywords: Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), teaching materials, achievement level, quality and effectiveness, assessment, individual assessment

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются критерии оценки уровня усвоения учащимися учебных материалов на основе международной программы оценки «Программа международной оценки образовательных достижений учащихся» (PISA).

Ключевые слова: Программа международной оценки образовательных достижений учащихся (PISA), учебные материалы, уровень успеваемости, качество и эффективность, оценка, индивидуальная оценка.

In international experience, assessment of students' knowledge in the educational process is carried out in various forms. It is manifested in the form of an evaluative influence of the teacher on students using student assessment criteria and does not reflect the knowledge, skills and qualifications of students, but rather indicates the possession of a certain partial knowledge or skill, not a subject. Assessment in the pedagogical process not only affects the educational process, but also leads to a change in the relationship between teachers and students, an increase in student motivation for educational activities. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 on the “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” sets out tasks such as the development and implementation of a national program to develop human capital and improve the quality of education. In implementing these priorities, the International Association for Educational Assessment (IEA), the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and international research on the international assessment program, as well as cooperation with international organizations, are aimed at monitoring the level of formation of relevant knowledge, skills and competencies of students in accordance with state educational standards, ensuring the constant preparation of students for lessons in academic subjects, ensuring the accuracy, reliability and simplicity of assessing their knowledge, skills and

competencies, ensuring compliance with assessment principles, and systematically analyzing the processes of formation of students' knowledge, skills and competencies. The idea of the PISA study is to test students' knowledge and skills based on internationally established indicators, their ability to think outside the scope of educational topics, creatively apply their knowledge in new situations, and demonstrate effective learning strategies. In this context, the assessment criteria of the PISA study reflect the following:

Reading literacy: The ability of a person to understand and respond to information presented in text form, to use the information he has read for his own purposes in the process of active participation in society, and to increase his knowledge and capabilities.

Mathematical literacy: Tests whether a person knows the place of mathematics in the world in which he lives, and whether he can correctly and completely justify mathematical processes. The main emphasis is on the ability to use mathematical knowledge in various life situations using different methods that require thinking and intuitive decision-making.

Scientific literacy: The competence to identify problems in life phenomena that can be solved scientifically, and to draw conclusions based on observations and experiments.

1. Current control - the knowledge, skills and abilities of students are regularly monitored in the form of questionnaires, control works or tests.
2. Intermediate control - at the end of the quarter and after completing the relevant section of the curriculum, in order to assess the knowledge, skills and abilities of students and in the form of control works or tests.
3. Phased control - at the end of the school year, in the form of oral and written exams and tests. On this basis, a rating is determined and a decision is made to transfer the student to the next grade. In short, PISA aims to evaluate education systems around the world by testing the skills and knowledge of 15-year-old students and can identify educational achievements and shortcomings through comparisons between countries.

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